

The microscopic and nanoscopic world made global

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Graphical abstract

Emerging image sharing and reusing in microscopy

The system: HELLO, HOW CAN I HELP YOU?

Researcher: I need images of microspheres, bearing a hierarchical two-level roughness, of any material, of sizes about 300 microns or lower.

The system: HERE YOU ARE (34 results)

Graphical abstract: Representation of the current movement to share and reuse the images obtained by microscopes from all over the world, as well as the development of intelligent image search engines for supporting the research workflow.

Motivation of this note

Do you use microscopy intensively in your research? Do not tell me that you have never had the feeling that you have a lot of microscopy images and related data stored in a drawer and that you consider work and time wasted because it cannot be published due to lack of space, because the main study was rejected in a magazine and you have given up, or because you have not completed a certain study but that you think could be useful to other researchers who could start from them to devise other studies, confirm or complement other types of results, who knows? Fortunately, with the advent of online publishing, it is becoming more and more common for publishers not to limit the length of works, although

they are still in the minority.^{1,2}

The spatial and temporal resolution of modern instruments is increasing so much that we can obtain not only very high resolution images and in an increasingly automated way and without the intervention of the microscopist, but also follow microscopic processes at video-rate speeds.³ That is exactly what we need to reliably describe microscopic reality, but... we run the risk of dying of success. The amount of images and their heterogeneity can be so enormous that this generates the problem of how to manage such diversity, a problem that will require the development of new image-based statistical techniques (how to make the average or the statistical deviation of images? In the case of numbers, everyone knows that there are arithmetic means, standard deviations, statistical tests, etc. and if not, turn to SPSS or a statistician). We will surely see developments in this regard based on current advances in Big Data, Machine Learning or Artificial Intelligence In the coming years.⁴

The problems suffered by microscopists to describe a physical reality at scales of micrometers or nanometers in a reliable way is not new and it is also suffered, for example, by photojournalists and astronomers. The former investigate a reality on a scale comparable to that of the human being through photographs, while astronomers use optical and non-optical images to scrutinize a reality on cosmic scales. They are all facing an enormously heterogeneous reality (Fig. 1). Who has not felt inopportune at some time by the image of our study selected for a graphical abstract? Is any image of a study really a graphic abstract? It is difficult to recognize that we all run the risk of getting a false impression of a photographed system (be it a region at war or a region of outer universe) by the image that is selected when associated with the report/study (a picture is worth a thousand words, for better or worse).⁵ But, space is precious, and it is the publishers who force to limit the space of the publications and the authors are forced to choose from the vast amount of material captured by our microscopes, with subjective criteria.

Figure 1. A representation of the representation of professionals who are dedicated to portraying the physical reality through images: microscopists, photojournalists and astronomers.

Research of the microscopic and nanoscopic world is intensive in the use of high resolution microscopy and therefore in data volume, so that in a golden moment of the open access science movements and in general of the transparency of the generation of scientific knowledge, an automated and general-use repository (going beyond the Supporting Info files) was lacking. If what you are concerned about is also getting due credit for your images, there is also good news in this regard: more and more of these currently maturing repositories are also becoming publishers. DOIs are associated with your image and with it your work is permanently citable. Needless to say, in this way many deposited images will be cited, thus multiplying the use of these repositories. For this to become a reality, apart from the willingness of the researchers to communicate not only what is published in the papers but also everything that is not included and may be useful, the engagement of the publishers is also required. These are increasingly sensitive to this enormous potential of unpublished raw data. The data that are published in the peer-reviewed journals are, let's say, compressed in the form of statistical parameters. Therefore, publishers are issuing new journals more focused on data, including microscopy images.

Repositories

There are currently several options to choose a repository to send (and annotate) the images produced by the research group where we work. It can be said that they are in the process of maturing, although it is obvious that the future that awaits them is bright. Just one fact: the volume of data deposited in some exceeds several petabytes, PB (1 PB = 10^6 GB = 10^3 TB)! An enormous benefit is produced to the common knowledge: not only because of the options of opening the knowledge to others, but because of the possibility that others reuse our image datasets for potential new discoveries and the development of new technologies or new scanning methods based on machine learning that are hungry for raw images to develop.⁶ Also it is more than possible that they become self-sustaining as profitable companies. It is to be hoped that robust repositories of microscopy images will follow the path of other similar initiatives already mature in the field of bioinformatics such as GenBank or Protein Data Bank.

Let's see a nice example of the use of a repository that has been highlighted by the media⁷: the group of Gabriel Lander, an expert in structural biology who works at Scripps Research in La Jolla (USA), uploaded data to one of these resources (EMPIAR, see below). The data was consulted by Sjors Scheres, who also works in structural biology at the University of Cambridge (UK), who was developing a method to refine Cryo-EM images. Using the Lander images, it was possible to increase the resolution of the images, which were already very high, by 35%, reaching a final resolution of 3.1 Å from initial data with a resolution of 2.3 Å.

Let's now pay attention to the repositories that are currently most in vogue, starting with the all-science, all-techniques ones. Why these? Because that is obviously where we can find everything. With the increase in information processing power, there is less and less need for specialized online forums or research journals. To put it in some way, what used to be the issues of a magazine (where we read the up-to-date information of a subject) are today the search results of search engines. That is why more and more all-science online

publications are emerging (Plos One, iScience, Scientific Reports, ACS Omega, Faculty of 1000, ...) with increasingly advanced search (or "thinking") technologies.

These are today the most important public repositories where we can send, consult, analyse and download microscopy images.

1. Figshare.

Figshare (<https://figshare.com/>) is a general type repository and accepts files of up to 5 GB at no cost; sometimes they accept larger files in exchange of a fee. Regarding the citability of the deposited material it must be said that all the content deposited in this repository is assigned a DOI and a bibliographic reference that points directly to the deposited content. In addition, Figshare allows search engines to explore within the deposited document and not only the page produced by Figshare. A point of course important if what you are looking for is to make our work more found by the community! In the event that the person who uploads the content to this repository so wishes, the content deposited can be made freely accessible while the copyright is secured thanks to the creative commons licenses provided by Figshare. In addition to images, you can also upload congress desserts, observations, statistical tables, audios and videos. Quite a temptation! Finally we can mention that Fisher has signed contracts with universities, sponsors, and this is the most interesting thing with publishers that include some big names like Springer Nature. Figshare can be used simply within the manuscript submission system, making it easier to share your research data and comply with journal and funder policies. Authors retain control over the data, which are stored privately until formal release of the publication.⁸

2. Image Data Resource (IDR).

This is a life-science only resource (<https://idr.openmicroscopy.org>). IDR enables the community to search, view, extract, and even process and analyze large, complex, and multidimensional life science image data, enabling validation of experimental methods and conclusions of scientific papers. It covers a variety of techniques, including multi-dimensional microscopy and digital pathology. IDR can be used without any special knowledge, but we can get more out of the data deposited in this repository (for example, make new discoveries or analyses) if we become familiar with how it is built (read Nature Methods⁹). The IDR datasets are accompanied by metadata provided by the authors, which can be annotations, defined regions, or ontological annotations, and other controlled ontologies. All of them are saved and are available for use in searches. IDR also contains a virtual environment to analyze the deposited data. Links to external resources (NCBI , PubChem) are also frequent. It currently contains 319 TB of multidimensional images and around 1M of different experiments on human, Drosophila, budding and fission yeast, and mouse cells and tissue, receiving a whopping 2500 unique visits per week.

3. Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB).

This is a public repository for 3D electron microscopy (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb>). The 2017 Nobel Prize in Chemistry was awarded "for developing cryo-electron microscopy for

high-resolution structural determination of biomolecules in solution." This award is an example of the spectacular growth that the development of this technique has had in recent years and triggered the use and amount of material deposited in this repository. The cumulative total number of entries in EMDB in 2020 was over 13,000, up from "only" 3,500 in 2015! It covers a variety of techniques, including single particle analysis, electron tomography, and electron crystallography. EMDB was founded in 2002. As of January 2021, EMDB is operated under the auspices of the World Protein Data Bank (wwPDB), and has also joined that organization as a full member.

4. Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR).

This is a life sciences only data repository (<https://empiar.org/>, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar>). EMPIAR is a free access archive of electron microscopy data of biological entities, both at the molecular and cellular level, deposited in the Electron Microscopy Data Bank, EMDB.¹⁰ Currently supported data types are Electron cryo-microscopy (EM), Electron cryo-tomography, Scanning EM (FIB SEM, SBF SEM, array tomography), Soft X-ray tomography, X-ray microscopy. The goal is to make available global data from current and state-of-the-art research, the development of new methods (for example, based on machine learning or AI, which are gaining momentum and becoming prominent and widely used techniques), the re-use of data and its validation by the community. The deposited data can be used without any restriction under a common creative license. It was established in 2014, with funding coming from the MRC and BBSRC. From 2021 it is financed through the Wellcome Trust, the UK Government, and receives funds corresponding to the member states of the EMBL. As of 2022-07-18, EMPIAR contains 954 entries, representing a deposited data volume of 1.94 PB (petabytes).

5. BioImage Archive (BIA).

The BioImage Archive¹¹ is a new (2020) archive of biological images at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive>. The BIA's scope is bioimaging data from molecule to organism scale, from any imaging modality, in any format that is associated with a publication, or of value beyond a single experiment. All data submitted to the BioImage Archive must be consented for a public. It is funded by the UK Government and receives funding from the EMBL member states.

Other repositories

The cell: an image library-CCDB (CIL-CCDB), <http://www.cellimagelibrary.org>: all forms of microscopy: 12.000 datasets, 30 TB of data.

The YRC Public Image Repository (YRC PIR), <https://images.yeastrc.org>: fluorescent microscopy only, 1.348.013 images, ~2.4 TB of data

Conclusions

To conclude, we can celebrate that data and metadata-rich microscopy image repositories are clearly on the rise and large institutions and companies, including the currently most important academic publishers, are betting on the implementation of this type of very complex repositories. As can be expected, the today most powerful repositories are those related to structural biology data obtained by EM techniques, which is pioneering in bioinformatics. But, will it take a long time for a repository capable of hosting data of any type of technique applied to any type of sample to appear? Let's hope not. This would undoubtedly accelerate a large number of innovations and discoveries also in areas such as physical and material sciences. This is actually what motivated me, back in 2002, to launch a series of microscopy books focused on the publication of general information, or to delve into exposing experimental procedures in detail, not necessarily suitable for publication in traditional journals, which in many cases gave rise to enormously successful works, such as Raposo et al.¹², with 204 citations, Sanchez et al.¹³, with 148 citations, to highlight a couple of them in non-biological fields. That said, good luck to the new entrepreneurs of the world of repositories!

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